

CHILDREN'S NUTRITIONAL STATUS AT SCHOOL

¹Karimova Z.Sh., ²Shaislamova G.S.

^{1,2}Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

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Abstract. *School-age children's dietary state affects their health, cognitive function, and ultimately their academic performance. For underprivileged kids, the school is a great place to offer nutrition and health services. However, school-age children are rarely included in nutrition and health surveys. It is impossible to get a current picture of their nutritional state worldwide. The aim of this paper is to highlight public health concerns and give an overview of the most recent data on the nutritional condition of school-age children in emerging and transitional nations.*

Keywords: *dietary intake, nutritional risk factors, living condition.*

Relevance. According to the data that is currently available, school-aged children in the regions under evaluation have a significantly poor nutritional status. In populations from South-East Asia and Africa, underweight and thinness were most common, while in Latin America, these conditions were often less than 10% of the population. Moderate (> 20%) or severe (> 40%) anemic prevalence was reported in more than half of the anemia investigations. Deficiencies in iron, iodine, zinc, and vitamin A were frequently reported to have prevalences of 20% to 30%. Latin American nations have the greatest rates of overweight (20–35%). In the Eastern Mediterranean, Asia, and Africa, the incidence of overweight was often less than 15%.

Malnutrition is a public health concern among school-age children in developing and transitional nations, according to the statistics currently available. However, there is a dearth of information accessible, particularly about micronutrient status. These results highlight the need for more high-caliber studies to evaluate the nutritional status of school-aged children as well as for nutrition interventions in this age group.

The purpose of this study. Therefore, the goal of this study was to use a joint baseline survey to ascertain the health and nutritional status of kids who were internally displaced in both the Western and Southern regions of Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods of research. In many places, undernutrition—which is characterized by a lack of nutrients and restricted access to healthful foods—remains a serious problem. This silent catastrophe affects children's vulnerability to infections, their physical and cognitive development, and their risk of morbidity and mortality. It shows itself as stunting, wasting, and nutritional deficiencies. Chronic undernutrition causes stunting, which impairs not just physical development but also cognitive function, academic performance, and future economic productivity. When a person consumes more calories than their body needs for energy expenditure and metabolic processes, it is referred to as overnutrition.

This frequently results in weight increase and can cause a number of health problems, including metabolic disorders, diabetes, cardiovascular illnesses, and obesity. Thus, excessive calorie intake, imbalanced dietary patterns, and sedentary lifestyles are the main causes of overnutrition in school-age children in developing countries, which shows up as conditions like overweight and obesity. This food imbalance makes health issues worse and emphasizes how urgently comprehensive therapies that address lifestyle and dietary choices are needed. Malnutrition in overweight people also highlights the complexity of nutritional status because

being overweight does not always mean that one is consuming enough of the necessary nutrients, which can conceal underlying deficits and present further health problems.

The coexistence of undernourished and overnourished people adds to the dual burden of malnutrition and further muddies the picture of world health. Non-communicable diseases linked to overnutrition have become serious hazards to children and adolescents, highlighting how urgent it is to address this problem. Laboratory tests of serum protein, serum lipids, serum micronutrient levels, and immunological markers are used in biochemical assessment to determine particular dietary deficits as well as to evaluate overall nutritional status. Measurements of albumin, prealbumin, hemoglobin, serum iron, total iron-binding capacity, magnesium, vitamin levels, trace elements, cholesterol, triglycerides, fasting glucose, CD4, CD8, HIV virus load, renal function, and liver enzyme levels are among the specific laboratory tests that are most commonly used.

A physical examination and a medical history are part of the clinical assessment process, which looks for indicators of or causes of malnutrition. Physical appearance, the assessment of comorbid illnesses and opportunistic infections, the presence of diarrhea, signs of malabsorption or gastrointestinal distress, pharmaceutical use, the use of herbal or nutritional supplements, and functional level are all important components of the clinical evaluation. In assessing nutritional risk factors, the evaluation of social, psychological, and economical resources that may impact a person's capacity to acquire, prepare, and consume food is just as crucial as the medical evaluation.

The nutritional assessment's dietary intake component looks at the present diet's sufficiency in terms of both macronutrient and micronutrient composition, identifies factors that affect acceptable intake, and finds food intolerances that may impact intake and appropriate prescription regimens. Determining steps that could enhance a patient's general health and preventing weight and lean body mass loss are the objectives of nutritional evaluation, followed by education and counseling. For a baseline assessment, it has been demonstrated that 24-hour recollection and diet history both yield reliable estimates of dietary consumption; these approaches perform well when compared to weighed food records and food frequency questionnaires.

Children's biochemical evaluation involves laboratory tests that are comparable to those performed on adults. It is necessary to take into account the nutritional implications of laboratory values in relation to other nutritional evaluation criteria. Children's particular clinical assessment characteristics include a thorough medical history and physical examination. The existence of gastrointestinal disorders or opportunistic infections that impact dental health, neurological disorders, behavioral problems, developmental evaluation, and nutritional health is given particular consideration. Perinatal variables that may impact eating ability, growth, and development in infants include the mother's nutrition, drug or alcohol exposure, birth weight, and birth history. The psychological environment, cultural customs, financial situation, and caregiver's health all have an impact on dependent children's nutritional status.

When children's food intake is evaluated, previous intake is reviewed, current intake is examined, macronutrient and micronutrient requirements and ability to satisfy them are assessed, and nutritional issues are identified. Important topics that need to be investigated are as follows:

- appetite, expression of hunger, and satiety
- duration of meals and feeding dynamics between child and caregiver
- feeding ability and tolerance
- appropriateness of infant diet and preparation of infant formula
- use of appropriate food and water safety strategies

- quality of diet and food availability

Malnutrition among school-age children in developing nations is caused by a variety of risk factors. The frequency of malnutrition is greatly influenced by demographic characteristics, such as parental unemployment or particular occupational position, nuclear or big family sizes, poor family income, higher socioeconomic class, and parental educational attainment. Important roles are also played by environmental factors such living conditions, household cleanliness, and the type of dwelling (rural or urban). The risk is further increased by knowledge of nutrition, eating patterns, nutrient deficits, degree of physical activity, and underlying medical disorders. Malnutrition's effects on health are diverse and include anything from fetal/maternal health and morbidity to a weakened overall state of health and particular dietary deficits. Additionally, malnutrition has a significant negative impact on academic performance and attendance, as well as cognitive abilities.

Living in flood-prone locations, having poor sanitation, and not having access to clean water are examples of environmental issues that are common in many developing nations. Children's health is greatly impacted by these difficulties, increasing their vulnerability to illnesses that worsen malnutrition. Fighting malnutrition in these situations requires actions to enhance living conditions by provide safe housing, sanitary facilities, and clean water. Results pertaining to healthcare highlight systemic problems with cultural norms, information gaps, and insufficient access to healthcare. Malnutrition is sustained by inadequate breastfeeding techniques and a lack of information about appropriate nutrition. These issues are frequently made worse by a lack of access to medical facilities and health education, which highlights the need for easily available and culturally aware healthcare solutions.

Both cultural preferences and financial limitations are reflected in the dietary practices of school-age children in developing nations. Limited access to a variety of nutrient-dense food sources is frequently the cause of food insecurity, dietary monotony, and an inadequate intake of vital nutrients. In addition to poverty, cultural customs and food availability also have an impact on the lack of nutritional diversity. Malnutrition is further exacerbated by children's sedentary lifestyles and lack of physical activity. This is caused by a number of things, such as a lack of infrastructure for leisure pursuits, worries about outside safety, and a lack of understanding of the value of exercise.

Conclusion. A complex interaction of socioeconomic, environmental, and health-related factors contributes to the widespread problem of malnutrition among school-age children in developing nations. The nutritional quality and general well-being of children are greatly impacted by these complex risk factors, which have their roots in poverty, limited access to healthcare, environmental issues, and lifestyle dynamics. The health effects range from short-term respiratory and gastrointestinal problems to long-term effects on mother health, intergenerational health, and cognitive development. Beyond its deleterious effects on health, malnutrition also has a negative impact on educational results, such as cognitive capacities, academic performance, and school attendance, which furthers cycles of disadvantage among disadvantaged groups.

In order to address these issues, comprehensive policy measures that support gender equality, increased healthcare access, nutritional literacy, poverty reduction, and sanitation must be in line with the SDGs. To lessen the negative impacts of malnutrition on school-age children, community-based initiatives, specialized interventions, and cooperation between sectors and international organizations are essential. Even though this study provides insightful information,

to improve our knowledge and develop more efficient methods of preventing malnutrition in these susceptible populations, future research should concentrate on longitudinal studies, interventional studies, and greater inclusivity in populations and languages. According to this study, 85.71% of schools provided meals that met at least one-third of the energy needs of the students.

None of the schools provide the micronutrients (iron, vitamin A, and vitamin C) that students require. There was no discernible difference in the two groups' dietary diversity. The nutritional value of meals prepared by PNASI kitchens has never been studied before, and this is the first study to do so. Policymakers are advised by the report to reevaluate and revamp the National Integrated School Feeding Program. The nutritional value of the meals provided in the PNASI canteen and their impact on the dietary diversity of schoolchildren are being evaluated for the first time in this study. Even though the food provided to schoolchildren does not meet one-third of the children's needs, the energy intake and adequacy of the meal are generally satisfactory. However, the food's micronutrient content and adequacy are extremely low. The results indicate that primary schools should implement a multi-strategy solution that includes school garden installation and nutritional teaching.

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